

VIEWS OF NEW ENLIGHTENMENTALISTS ON FORMING THE MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article reflects the views of the New Enlightenment thinkers Abdulla Avloni, Mahmudkhoj Behbudi, Abdurauf Fitrat on spiritual and moral education. The main directions of child education, the great importance of moral education in school and family for society are discussed in detail..

Keywords: Jadid, enlightenment, spirituality, spiritual and moral upbringing, education, family, school, Mahmudkhoj Behbudiy, Abdulla Avloniy, Abdurauf Fitrat, "Turkish Rose Garden or Morality", "Padarkush".

The radical changes that took place in the social life of Turkestan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, especially the strengthening of the Enlightenment movement, laid the foundation for the formation of new views on the upbringing of the younger generation. In this process, the Jadid Enlightenment played a special role, who, along with reforming the education system and arming students with modern knowledge, also paid great attention to their moral development. In the eyes of the Jadids, educating the younger generation included not only providing knowledge, but also raising them in the spirit of high moral qualities such as patriotism, honesty, hard work, and humanity.

By updating teaching methods in schools and madrasas, they set the main goal of awakening the minds of students, teaching them to think independently, and educating a well-rounded individual who would serve the development of society. The relevance of this topic is that even today, national values, historical heritage, and the progressive ideas of the new enlighteners play an important role in shaping the moral education of students. By studying their views on education and combining them with the modern pedagogical process, it is possible to educate the younger generation as fully mature people. Therefore, in this work, the ideas of the new enlighteners for the education of students views on the formation of moral education, their content and significance in today's education system are analyzed. Thought education is an important factor in raising a child to the level of a perfect person. The main responsibility for implementing this task falls on the teacher. Because during the lesson, the teacher teaches students to think, to deeply perceive the essence of any event. In this regard, Abdulla Avloni attaches special importance to the unity of education and upbringing

Only through the education of thought, which is an expression of mental activity, does a person achieve great honor and perfection, in this regard, the breadth of the teacher's thinking, the high level of knowledge in all respects are of decisive importance in the education of students. Developing the ability to think leads to acting with reason. It teaches students to distinguish between good and bad behavior, to acquire good behavior necessary for a perfect person, and to stay away from bad behavior that leads a person to misguidance. In the chapter "Good Manners" of his work, Abdulla Avloni discusses in detail human qualities such as religion, Islam, modesty, contentment, courage, patience, discipline, conscience, love of homeland, truthfulness, chastity, preservation of language, and loyalty. To prove his views, he cites examples from the verses of the Holy Quran, Hadith Sharif, and the thoughts of great thinkers Plato, Aristotle, Socrates, Ibn Sina, Mevlana Rumi, Sheikh Sa'di, Alisher Navoi, and Bedil. Developing the ability to think in children, organizing the education of thought is a very necessary and sacred duty.

For this reason, our great scholars paid special attention to intellectual education. Avloni, relying on the affirmations accumulated in virtues and wisdom, says the following about intellectual education: "Intellectual education is the most necessary, a sacred task that has been appreciated for a long time, which has been the focus of teachers and is entrusted to their conscience. The environment in which a child is brought up, that is, the family, plays an important role in increasing the child's interest and desire for knowledge. It is emphasized that the most effective way for a child to witness that parents are educated in the family, and that parents themselves are an example and a living example in upbringing is to develop a child's regular reading in the family. Parents should work hard for this. Children are also different. There are children who share their mother's happiness and leave her alone in her misfortune. There are also children who only love the charming nature and gardens of the homeland, but do not think about its worries and sorrows. One must love the homeland, no matter what it is. "Just as we, - says Avloni, - Turkestanis love our homeland more than our own lives, Arabs love their Arabian lands, the hot sandy deserts, and Eskimos love the northern regions, the coldest snow and ice lands more than other places. If they did not love it, they would have left their homeland and emigrated to places with better weather and easier living conditions." Our ancestors used to say, "Be a shepherd in your own country until you become a sultan in a neighboring country." Abdulla Avloni agrees with all thinkers that it is better to start raising children in the family early, and believes that since the role of education in a person's adulthood is incomparable, this process should be carried out based on ancient traditions. One of the founders and leaders of the Jadid movement in Turkestan, Mahmudkhodja Behbudi, seeks to realize all his goals only through enlightenment. One of the founders and leaders of the Jadid movement in Turkestan, Mahmudkhodja Behbudi, seeks to realize all his goals only through enlightenment. He deeply understood that the development of society, the prosperity of the nation, and the freedom of the people are directly related to science and education. Therefore, he criticized the old-style education system and paid great attention to the organization of new-style schools, the creation of textbooks, and the education of the younger generation based on modern knowledge. Behbudi emphasizes in his works the need for young people to be not only knowledgeable, but also to have high moral qualities. In his opinion, a truly perfect person is a person who is knowledgeable, patriotic, honest, and able to feel his responsibility to society. He also notes that the role of the teacher in the educational process is invaluable, and calls on teachers to work on themselves

and keep up with the times As the main way to implement his ideas on education, he advocated the opening of new schools, teaching young people not only religious sciences but also exact sciences, and the widespread introduction of European education in the countries of Turkestan, and called on the local population to engage in science and enlightenment. In the fight against colonialism, darkness, ignorance, and backwardness, he relied solely on science and enlightenment, directing his efforts and abilities to the development of schools, education, religious, natural sciences, and enlightenment. In the play "Padarkush," written in 1911, Behbudi sharply raised the issues of science, enlightenment, enlightenment, and in general, public education and pedagogical issues that had a scientific basis. In particular, the work puts forward the moral concept that if the educational requirements of the school and the family are not the same, if the parents pull their child in a different direction, the child's upbringing will be completely disrupted. "Padarkush" is essentially an artistic expression of pedagogical views, which also reflects the negative impact of the historical conditions in colonial Turkestan on the life of the local population and the upbringing of young people. This shows us that Behbudi's pedagogical views have always been connected with the most important and complex problems in social life, with the politics of his time.

Another prominent representative of the Jadids, Abdurauf Fitrat, considered education to be very important in enlightening the people. Fitrat mentioned all the schools in Bukhara in his works, but he said that education had no importance in the formation of moral qualities. Fitrat considered the school to be a center of education, emphasizing that the school is one of the main sources ensuring the development of social life.

He believes that the school should educate children and eliminate corruption, theft, and filth in society. Fitrat cites many stories in his textbooks, in which he tries to provide moral education and instill various moral qualities. Fitrat is a skilled educator who fought for the education of the human personality. Based on the values of nationalism and patriotism, he created a doctrine that can be an important guide in creating a patriotic ideology and teaching young people to love their homeland and nation. Fitrat considers homeland, patriotism and humanity to be the highest moral qualities and calls on people to protect it and serve it wholeheartedly.

One of the most important issues in Fitrat's work is that he deeply studied and analyzed the ideas of Islam from all sides and advocated their use in raising a perfect person with faith and honesty. Fitrat considers the role of moral education

to be very important in the upbringing of a perfect person. In his opinion, the task of moral education is to raise a person to be morally perfect and useful to everyone. He considers wisdom, chastity, courage and justice to be the main moral qualities. Fitrat also focuses on the issues of family education and the role of women in society. He shows that the role of the mother in raising a child is very important. At the same time, he substantiates the need for cooperation between the family, school and state in upbringing. Fitrat's work "The Leader of Salvation" is entirely devoted to the issues of education and upbringing. In the chapter "Issues of Child Education" of this work, he emphasizes that "One of the tasks of the family is to raise the generation." In addition, he emphasizes that child rearing should not be the sole responsibility of the family, but should also be the responsibility of the wider community and the state, because the future of the state lies in the hands of such young people.

Fitrat emphasizes that children receive their upbringing from the environment they live in and the children around them. He proves that the social environment has a great influence on a child's upbringing. Fitrat wrote in his work: "There is no nation in the world that does not seek honor and happiness. The happiness and honor of every nation, of course, depends on the internal discipline and harmony of this nation. Peace and harmony, in turn, rely on the discipline of the families of this nation. Fitrat considers it a very correct action to not allow people with corrupt morals to approach not only the teaching profession at school, but also the school security guard. In his works, he glorifies the ideas of patriotism, humanity, freedom, hard work, striving for a goal, being kind to people, and putting the interests of the people above one's own interests.

Abdurauf Fitrat, as one of the figures who tirelessly promoted the problems of achieving national independence and the fight against colonialism throughout his life, and learning from the science and technology culture of European countries, is a great inspiration to everyone, especially the youth. is an example.

Conclusion. Well-rounded, purposeful and energetic young people who have knowledge and skills, who can take responsibility for the worthy future of the country, emerge only when moral education is properly established in the family. Spiritual and moral education does not form by itself, in order to form it, parents must engage with their children and have good manners themselves, as well as not be indifferent to their environment.

Today, the invaluable works, scientific, poetic and prose heritage, socio-philosophical and moral ideas of enlightened Jadids serve the spiritual enlightenment of the Uzbek people, raise national education, national values and

national consciousness, and cultivate feelings of love and loyalty to the Motherland in the hearts of young people. Their worldviews His spiritual and moral thoughts are still preserved as the cultural and spiritual values of our people.

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